

Impacts of earlier natural gas phase-out & heat-saving policies on district heating and the energy system

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ABSTRACT

Decarbonizing the district heating sector is essential for an affordable energy transition. Decarbonization strategies focusing on the interaction between power sector, individual heating technologies, heat-saving measures, and district heating expansion are missing in literature. We use energy system investment optimization to analyse the impact of decarbonization policies on district heating by comprehensively modelling the above-mentioned interaction across power and heating sector, and within the heating sector. We model decarbonization policy scenarios of massive investment into heat-saving measures and an earlier natural gas phase-out by 2030. Using Denmark as a case study, we identify policy-driven investments into heat-saving measures as non-optimal. Our results indicate that district heating expansion facilitates an earlier natural gas phase-out, which is a viable policy that inflicts only 0.07% extra system cost compared to a scenario with only net-zero emission targets. Furthermore, we find that decarbonized district heating sector has a very high reliance on industrial excess heat, bio-fuels, and electrification. A biomass tax reduces the high utilization of raw biomass and promotes its more sustainable use in carbon capture and storage. Our results show a cogeneration capacity reduction, which poses a challenge to the business model of conventional Danish district heating companies.

1. Introduction

District heating (DH) is an underground piping system that supplies hot water to buildings to fulfil space heating, hot water demand, or both. DH consists of a distribution network, and sometimes a transmission network, with centralized units producing heat. Unlike a power supply network connecting an entire country, the DH supply network is limited and localized, supplying heat only to a city or to a particular city district.

DH plays an essential role in making an energy system sustainable because it is an efficient way of using low-grade energy for heating purposes. Compared to individual heating units, the numerous benefits of using a DH system include enabling the use of local energy sources especially, waste or excess heat that alone can fulfil the heating demand of all buildings in the European Union (EU) (European Commission, 2016). Moreover, DH, which is often referred to as the central heat supply, reduces or eliminates local pollution from individual heating units such as boilers or burners. Furthermore, a centralized heat supply is more robust than individual units because it makes switching to a

green and sustainable fuel at a central plant easier and can leverage from the fuel diversity. Similarly, DH offers a cheaper heat supply in densely populated urban areas than other heating alternatives, thereby eliminating energy poverty and ensuring a competitive local economy (UNEP District Energy Initiative, 2015).

The importance of DH in the decarbonization has recently been recognized at the EU institutional level, with EU state aid rules allowing member states to support DH projects as defined in Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) (European Commission, 2014). Moreover, as an energy-efficient DH contributes to the EU energy efficiency target of a 32.5% reduction of final energy use by 2030, the 2021 European Green Deal investment plan gives member states even more flexibility to support district heating generation (Richter, 2020).

Substantial potential for DH exists in the EU for decarbonizing the heat and cooling sector to meet the EU's 2050 zero-carbon target. According to HEAT Roadmap Europe, the EU can affordably decarbonize its energy system by expanding DH in urban areas, thereby meeting 50% of the EU's total heat demand (Mathiesen et al., 2019). DH is popular in

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the Nordic countries, especially in Sweden and Denmark, covering 55% and 65% of the heating demand, respectively. As the DH in these countries has evolved over decades with strong governmental support, such a multi-fuel DH has contributed to reducing the national CO₂ emissions and improving the overall efficiency of the energy system (Di Lucia and Ericsson, 2014; Münster et al., 2012).

Despite its many benefits, the DH sector faces the challenge of decarbonization along with the whole energy sector. Furthermore, the competitiveness of DH relative to other decentralized individual heating technologies depends on heat demand density which can be reduced by aggressive energy renovations of building stock. This reduction challenges the business model of conventional DH companies. Furthermore, natural gas is an essential part of European energy generation mix and large parts of this gas comes from Russia. The post covid supply crunch and 2022 war between Ukraine and Russia has further aggravated the situation to a point where natural gas supply is no longer considered reliable (Lee, 2021). The recent calls for natural gas phase-out from the European energy system (Commission E, 2022; Wienberg, 2022), adds to the list of challenges faced by DH.

On the supply side, the DH sector is closely coupled with the power sector due to very high share of cogeneration (CHP) based capacity. On the demand side, DH competes with individual heating technologies (e.g., individual heating boilers), and investment in heat-saving measures. Therefore, studying the future development of the DH sector requires an energy system-wide perspective that incorporates the interaction between the heating and the power sector on the supply side and competition between individual heating technologies, and investment into heat-saving measures at the demand side. In this respect energy system models are valuable analysis tools. Therefore, in this paper, we use energy system modelling to analyse the decarbonization of district heating under different policy scenarios.

The literature on decarbonizing DH extensively uses large energy system models to study the DH sector's future technological development. While these models take the interconnection of power and the DH sector into account, they do not incorporate the full spectrum of competition for investments among (a) DH expansion, (b) individual heating technologies, and (c) heat-saving measures. Additionally, the literature is silent on the issue concerning the impact of an earlier phase-out of natural gas on the decarbonization of power and heating sector. This study addresses these issues.

By comprehensively modelling the above-mentioned heating sector dynamics in an energy system model, this paper analyses future decarbonization pathways for the DH sector under different decarbonization policy scenarios. These scenarios represent heat demand reduction resulting from policy-driven massive investments in heat-savings (energy renovation) and early phase-out of natural gas. Due to the 2022 global energy crisis, both of these policy targets have gained significant popularity. Therefore, this paper analyses these policy scenarios and answer the following questions:

- How do ambitious policy targets for heat savings and early phase-out of natural gas impact the DH sector's decarbonization?
- From an energy system perspective, which fuels and technologies enable the DH sector to achieve decarbonization?
- How does the competition from individual heating technologies and investment in heat savings impact the expansion of the DH sector?
- What are the implications of the paper's findings for policymakers and DH companies?

This paper considers Denmark as case study. However, the outcomes of this study can be generalized for other countries with substantial demand for space heating, especially true for north American, north and central European countries along with China and Japan. The insights from this study can help guide policymakers to understand the role of DH in decarbonizing the energy system.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. After the literature

review in chapter 2, chapter 3 introduces the methodology, the energy system model used in this study and its extensions. Chapter 4 introduces the Danish district heating sector as a case study and relevant assumptions used in the energy system model. Chapter 5 represents results followed by a discussion in chapter 6. Finally, chapter 7 concludes this study.

2. Literature review

DH sector is often considered to face competition from individual heating technologies, especially heat pumps. K Kontu et al. (2020) compare the profitability of connecting a new building with DH network with installing a ground source heat pump. They found that in Finland, ground-source heat pumps can be more profitable than DH. However, this study only considers small-size heat pumps meaning that heat pump only covers 97–98% of the heat demand of buildings and not the peak demand. M Åberg et al. (2020) study the competition between the ground-source heat pump and DH for Uppsala in Sweden. They find that DH faces no threat from ground source heat pumps in city centres with high urban density. This is due to the geological constraints of digging so many wells for individual heat pumps. At the European level, D. Connolly et al. (2014) find that DH, in combination with heat saving, can achieve the European Union emission reduction targets. This comes at 15% reduced cost for heating and cooling as compared to the scenario where the heat sector is electrified via individual electric boilers or heat pumps.

Quantitative models are extensively used for the studies related to DH. A popular category of these models focusses on optimization of technical operations of DH. They either involve optimization of hydraulic parameters, like flow temperature, flow rate, reduction of losses, or configuration of different system components, like the size of storage, diameters of network pipes, etc (Novitsky et al., 2020; Sarbu et al., 2019). Such models for operation optimization are outside of this paper's scope as this paper focuses on investment and the future development of a whole national DH sector based on the case of Denmark.

The second category of studies focuses on planning of the future development and expansion of the DH network mostly using Geographical Information System (GIS) based tools. Analyses in GIS can take transmission and distribution (T&D) constraints and spatial distribution of heat demand into account, which makes it a strong tool for the analysis of DH potential expansion (Petrovic and Karlsson, 2014a). GIS based tools are extensively used for calculating the potential of DH expansion which often relates to economic potential/feasibility rather than a technical feasibility (Petrovic and Karlsson, 2014a). This economic potential or feasibility is defined as heat supplied by DH after expansion being cheaper than a baseline individual heating technology or some generic price of heat paid by consumers prior to DH grid expansion. Such studies also calculate the cost of DH expansion, which may include the cost of transmission and distribution network, substation, connection cost, heat production cost, and capital expenses of investments in generation capacity.

Nielsen et al. (Nielsen and Möller, 2013), used GIS to map the existing DH network along with spatial distribution of heat demand to estimate the potential of DH expansion in Denmark. The study finds an expansion potential for DH from 40% share of residential heat supply to up to 63% share. Petrovic S et al. (Petrovic and Karlsson, 2014a) used GIS to calculate the cost of DH expansion in Denmark in three different areas; areas within the DH grid where heat demand is supplied by individual heating, areas nearby the existing DH grid, and other areas outside the DH grid. Petrovic S et al. (Petrovic and Karlsson, 2014b) used a similar approach to calculate the cost of energy renovations in residential buildings and found that if all the energy renovations are carried out in all the relevant buildings in Denmark, ignoring any cost constraints, a 75–85% of heat demand reduction can be achieved. Buhler F et al. (Bühler et al., 2017a) estimate the potential of industrial excess heat(EH) for district heating in Denmark by GIS mapping the existing

DH grid and spatial distribution of different industries with EH. They estimate a potential of about 1.36 TWh/year of EH that can be used for district heating. Similarly, Delmastro C et al. (Delmastro et al., 2017) and Nielsen S et al. (Nielsen and Grundahl, 2018) used GIS to study the impact of heat savings on DH.

These GIS based studies are, however, very sector specific and do not take into account the overall system perspective of energy system where power and heat sector are connected and influence each other. To take the energy system perspective into account, a number of energy system models exist that are used to study the future developments of the DH sector (Sperling and Möller, 2012, 2012b; Åberg and Henning, 2011; Sandvall et al., 2021). However, these energy systems models analyse the heating sector based on the estimates of the DH expansion cost and potential calculated from GIS based studies.

Sperling et al. (Sperling and Möller, 2012) use an energy system operation optimization model EnergyPLAN to study the impact of exogenous DH expansion and heat savings on the local energy system and local renewable energy production in the municipality of Frederikshavn in Denmark. They find that DH expansion in combination with heat savings leads to high fuel efficiency along with near-zero CO2 emissions and no net import of electricity to the local energy system. However, due to the short-term optimization horizon of 3–5 years, investments into new technologies and capacities are not considered. Similarly, Åberg M et al., 2011 (Åberg and Henning, 2011) use another local energy system operation optimization model to study the impact of exogenous heat savings in residential buildings on the DH system in the city of Linköping, Sweden. Such operation optimization models give a good understanding of the impact of DH expansion on existing energy systems. However, the optimization time horizon is often short-term. Future development of energy systems also requires investments into new technologies that need to be taken into account in long-term investment optimization models.

Sandvall A et al. (Sandvall et al., 2021) use TIMES for long-term investment optimization. The study only focuses on the utilization of low-temperature excess heat source with the help of heat pumps. Marie M et al. (Münster et al., 2012) use the investment optimization model Balmorel to study the future development trend of DH sector in the Danish energy system for medium time horizon till 2025. However, the impact of heat-saving measures on the district heating sector are not modelled. This is taken into account by Zvingilaite E et al. (Zvingilaite and Balyk, 2014), who develop an extension of Balmorel to study the investments into various HS measures/renovations and their impact on the energy sector; however, expansion of DH is taken as exogenous (not decided by the model itself).

Therefore, investment optimization of the energy system where the model endogenously determines investments into DH expansion, individual heating technologies, and heat-saving measures is lacking. The model developed in this paper brings such dynamics of the heating sector into the investment optimization of the whole energy system. Furthermore, the literature is silent on the earlier phase-out of natural gas and its impact on achieving decarbonization by 2050. Most of the literature and even policies have focused on earlier phase-out of coal while natural gas is always championed as a transitional fuel expected to be a part of the fuel mix for long-term leading to a lock in effect (Brauers et al., 2021), (Kemfert et al., 2022). However, the natural gas supply crisis at the onset of covid pandemic and 2022 war between Russia and Ukraine has rendered natural gas an unreliable fuel calling for its earlier phase-out. Therefore, this paper covers the gap on quantifying the impact of earlier natural gas phase-out on the decarbonization of the whole energy system.

3. Methodology

3.1. Investment optimization - model description

This study adopts energy systems investment optimization model

Balmorel. Balmorel is a partial equilibrium, deterministic energy system model with a detailed representation of the power and heating sector. It has a rolling horizon for investment optimization. It is open-source (Balmorel community 2022, 2022) and has been developed for the analysis of future development of the Danish and European energy system under different policy regimes (Wiese et al., 2018). It minimizes the cost by taking into account the socio-economic perspective under the constraint to meet heat and electricity demand. Fig. 1 represents the brief overview of Balmorel core structure. The generic objective function is as follow:

$$\text{Min } C = \sum_y C_y^{\text{inv}} + C_y^{\text{fix}} + C_y^{\text{var}} \quad 1.1$$

$$C_y^{\text{inv}} = C_y^{\text{exp}} + C_y^{\text{hs}} + C_y^{\text{tran}} + C_y^{\text{gen}} \quad 1.2$$

Where all the costs are discounted with discount rate of 4%. C_y^{inv} is discounted investment costs that are annualized over the technology lifetime and it includes all investments into generation technologies & storages C_y^{gen} , expansion of districting heating distribution grid C_y^{exp} , expansion of electricity transmissions network C_y^{tran} , renovation of buildings for energy savings C_y^{hs} , and so on. C_y^{var} includes carbon price, fuel price, and other operating costs specific to each technology operation. C_y^{fix} is the fixed O&M cost. More information on model formulation can be found here (Wiese et al., 2018).

The geographical boundaries are modelled as countries that consist of different regions, which are further divided into different areas. A graphical depiction of regions and areas are shown in Fig. 2. The regions within a country are similar to the bidding zone in Nord Pool electricity market, i.e., Denmark consists of two regions DK1 and DK2. For the power sector, each region represents the overall aggregated demand and the generation capacity present in that region. The electricity transmission between the region is constrained by the maximum transmission capacity with the possibility of future investment. The transmission and distribution network constrained within a region is not considered. The power sector of neighbouring countries and their interconnection with the Danish power system are modelled in detail in Balmorel (Wiese et al., 2018).

On the other hand, the heating sector is modelled at the geographical resolution of areas within a region. The heat demand and supply are aggregated in each area. There is no heat transmission between the areas, and distribution network constraints within an area, especially true for the areas supplied by district heating networks, are not modelled. A particular geographical area supplied by a district heating network, for example, can be modelled as a separate individual heating area in Balmorel or it can be combined with other similar geographical areas supplied by other DH networks and modelled as a joint single individual heating area in Balmorel. Therefore, the choice of the number of heating areas modelled depends on model complexity and resulting computing time and resources needed along with the availability of data. Usually, these areas are selected based on the approximation from some GIS study.

In this study, the future developments in the DH sector are studied by optimizing the investment into the energy system. To meet the heating demand, the model decides to invest either into individual heating technologies, energy-saving measures (buildings renovations), expansion of the existing DH network, and new generation capacity for DH. Thus, DH competes with individual heating technologies and/or heat-saving measures. The two new add-ons, which model the investments into DH expansion and heat-saving measures in Blamorel are developed for this study. These add-ons are explained below.

3.1.1. District heating expansion

This study models the expansion of the district heating network into individual heating areas. The expansion of district heating to buildings

Fig. 1. Overview of Balmore core structure (Wiese et al., 2018).

Fig. 2. Graphical depiction of modelling of geographical boundaries as regions and areas in Balmore.

that are either nearby or within an existing district heating network area is considered. The cost of district heating grid expansion for buildings within district heating network area only includes connection cost, while for those located near an existing district heating grid, the cost of distribution network expansion is included along with connection cost. Thus, only the expansion of the existing distribution grid is considered. A separate expansion cost for houses and apartments located in each DH network area is considered. The following equation adds the expansion of district heating to the objective function in equation (1.2):

$$C_y^{exp} = \sum_{r,a,e} (E_{y,r,a,e} * ec_{r,a,e}) \quad 2.1$$

$$\sum_y E_{y,r,a,e} \leq ep_{r,a,e} \quad 2.2$$

The subscript, r represents the regions while areas are represented by a which is further divided into DH areas and individual heating areas. e represents whether the expansion is inside the DH network or nearby. E is the decision variables representing the expansion of DH network and ec is the cost of expansion while ep is the total expansion potential.

Such expansion modifies the heat demand of district heating (dh) and individual heating (di) sectors from the exogenous heat demand (dhe & die), as shown in equations (2.3) and (2.4). These equations move the heat demand covered by the expanded DH network from individual heating areas to DH areas.

$$dh_y = dhe_y + E_{y-1} \quad 2.3$$

$$di_y = die_y - E_{y-1} \quad 2.4$$

3.1.2. Heat savings investment

The investment into residential heat-saving measures, or building renovations, is also optimized. The heat-saving investments result in reduced demand for heating. The heat-saving investment optimization includes buildings connected with the district heating networks and those that are not connected and use individual heating. The heat-saving investment includes changing windows and different levels of insulation for walls, ceiling, floor, and ventilation systems. An exponential relationship between the investment into heat savings measures and resulting heat-saving achieved is modelled by a piecewise linear function. The following equation adds heat saving investments to the objective function in equation (1):

$$C_y^{hs} = \sum_{r,a,st} (HS_{y,r,a,st} * hc_{y,r,a,st}) \quad 3.1$$

hc represents cost of heat savings while HS is the decision variable representing the total heating savings. st represents various steps that

approximate the exponential relationship (shown in appendix A.2). A fix amount of heat savings hs^{fix} can be defined. Under normal scenarios, this parameter is defined equal to zero. However, to study scenarios with policy driven targets for heat savings, this parameter can be changed to a desired value.

$$\sum_{y,r,a,st} HS_{y,r,a,st} \geq hs^{fix} \quad 3.2$$

The heat savings HS will affect the heat demand in individual heating areas ia and district heating areas id . The above equations (2.3) and (2.4) on heat demand are modified as follow:

$$dh_y = dhe_y + E_{y-1} - \sum_{a \in id} HS_{y-1,a} \quad 3.3$$

$$di_y = die_y - E_{y-1} \sum_{a \in ia} HS_{y-1,a} \quad 3.4$$

4. Case study & assumptions

About 64% of homes in Denmark are connected with DH, which covers more than half of the space heating demand in Denmark. The DH network in Denmark has one of the highest market shares in the world and it is also the most efficient network in the world. Therefore, the district heating sector in Denmark is chosen as a case study for this article.

4.1. Danish district heating system

The first collective heat supply in Denmark was established around the 1920s and 1930s using excess heat from a coal-fired power plant. The oil crisis and subsequent high energy prices in the early 1970s brought energy efficiency as the main focus to reduce dependence on imported fuels. Thereby, increasing reliance on CHPs and DH networks. This resulted in substantial uptake of CHP based DH supply where today, around 70% of heat in DH networks comes from CHPs (Danish Energy Agency et al., 2012). Denmark has six large central DH networks and over 400 smaller decentralized DH networks. DH network in Copenhagen is the largest with a transmission length of 50 Km (Danish Energy Agency et al., 2012).

DH in Denmark has a considerable share of renewable energy due to fuel switch in fossil fuel-based CHPs where tax exemption on biomass and further state subsidy on biomass-based electricity production led to the replacement of fossils with biomass. Such a high reliance on biomass for decarbonization has raised concern regarding its sustainability (Danish Energy Agency, 2020).

Denmark has a strong political will to move towards decarbonization. In June 2020, the Danish parliament set a target of 70% GHG emissions reduction by 2030, compared to 1990 levels, leading to zero GHG emissions till 2050 (Danish Ministry of Climate E& U, 2019). Further, the Danish government set forth target to decarbonize heat supply to buildings by 2035 (Kerr and Winskel, 2021). Such political commitments along with district heating being a major supply of heat, make it important to consider future development pathways for the district heating sector that aligns with the zero GHG emissions target.

4.2. Spatial resolution for Denmark in Balmorel

As mentioned earlier, Denmark is divided into two regions, DK1 (west) and DK2 (east), according to the Nord Pool bidding zones. Each region is further divided into a number of areas that can be grouped into two distinct groups; one set of areas representing the heat demand covered by supply from DH networks. The other represents heat demand of out-of-DH areas, supplied by individual heat technologies, mainly HP and boilers. Out of total 14 areas modelled, 10 represents DH areas and 4 represents individual heating areas. To model existing DH networks,

they are classified into different groups according to their size, i.e., large, medium, medium-small, etc. The individual heating areas can be further grouped into two groups, one represents the heat demand of individual family houses, and the other represents heat demand from apartments or multiple-story multi-family houses.

4.3. Heat demand assumption

The exogenous heat demand is shown in Fig. 3. There is a slight reduction in heat demand for district heating and the individual heating sector as it considers the energy efficiency gains. From 2020 onwards, about 0.2% reduction in heat demand is assumed for each year (Nordic Energy Research and IEA, 2016). Similarly, the demand for industrial process heating is projected to be reduced by 9% in 2050, as compared to 2020, due to energy efficiency gains (Kofoed-Wiuff et al., 2020).

4.4. District heating & heat-savings assumptions

The total expansion of the district heating network is capped to 2.1 TWh in DK1 and 4 TWh in DK2. These assumptions on expansion cost and expansion potential are calculated based on the methodology discussed in Petrovic et al. (Petrovic and Karlsson, 2014a) where a GIS based mapping of existing district heating network and heat demand density in Denmark is conducted to calculate the expansion potential and expansion cost. These assumptions are shown in appendix A1.

The heat savings measures considered in this model are related to buildings renovations that lead to lower heat loss and, thus, lower heat demand. Different level of insulation for walls, roof, floor, windows, and ventilation system is considered. The relationship between the marginal cost of energy renovations (different level of insulation) and the resulting reduction in heat demand is modelled as a piecewise exponential curve for each area, based on (Petrovic and Karlsson, 2014b). These exponential cost curves are shown in appendix A2.

4.5. Other assumptions – fuel prices & potentials

Table 1 represents the price assumption for some of the fuels. However, only for natural gas, coal, and oil different prices are used for different scenarios which are based on IEA world energy outlook 2022 (Agency IE, 2022). The difference fuel prices for natural gas, coal, and oil are shown in Table 2. The yearly consumption potential of municipal waste, straw, wood chips, and biogas is limited based on the locally available potential which is regarded as sustainably available potential (Harjanne and Korhonen, 2019). The detailed list of all the fuels considered along with their price assumptions is provided in appendix A3. Municipal waste has a negative price as waste incineration plants get paid for waste management (Münster and Meibom, 2011). For different technologies, the assumptions concerning costs and other technological parameters are taken from the technology catalogue provided by Danish Energy Agency (Danish Energy Agency, 2022). Carbon price or tax projections are motivated from the IEA world energy outlook 2022 net-zero emission scenario (Agency IE, 2022) and given in appendix A4.

All the main generation technologies that are currently present in the energy system of Denmark are included. For fossil fuel and biomass-based boilers and CHPs, the possibility of investment into carbon capture and storage is also modelled. New investment into coal-based CHPs are not allowed in any scenario as it is based on the Danish government plan to phase out coal production till 2030 (OECD, 2021). Both electricity and heat storage are considered. For heat storage, possible to invest in intra-seasonal (pit storage) and inter-seasonal (water tank storage) storage is considered.

This study does not consider different temperature regimes for the DH network, only conventional high temperature DH networks are consider. Some of the new innovative technologies like power generation from ocean waves, underwater turbines, and hydrogen heating etc are not considered. Existing capacity of geothermal is considered but no

Fig. 3. Exogenous heat demand projections.

Table 1

Different fuels included in the model along with their price assumption and yearly potential.

Fuel	Price assumption (€/GJ)				Maximum Potential (PJ/year)
	2020	2030	2040	2050	
Municipal waste ^a	-3.295	-3.295	-3.295	-3.295	40.7 (Nordic Energy Research and IEA, 2016)
Straw ^b	5.66	5.95	6	6.14	20 (Nordic Energy Research and IEA, 2016)
Wood chips ^b	6.56	6.96	7.28	7.28	40 (Nordic Energy Research and IEA, 2016)
Wood pellets ^b	8.57	9.15	9.25	9.35	-
Biogas ^c	9.997	9.997	9.997	9.997	16.8 (Scarlat et al., 2018)

^a Source: (Münster and Meibom, 2011).

^b Source: (Danish Energy Agency, 2021).

^c Source: (Jensen et al., 2017).

future investment is allowed due to lack of assumption on available geothermal potential and cost of generation.

The utilization of industrial excess heat is modelled exogenously. It takes into account the high-temperature excess heat from industries along with excess heat coming from future deployment of Power-to-x plants and bio-refineries (Bühler et al., 2017b; Energistyrelsen, 2021). Therefore, it is assumed that such industrial excess heat doesn't require any technology to boost its temperature before injecting it to DH grid (Energistyrelsen, 2021). Such exogenous uptake of excess heat in district heating systems will make up to 30% of the total heat supply by district heating networks in 2050. Therefore, to study the impact of such an assumption, a sensitivity analysis is included by reducing this exogenous uptake of excess heat by 50%. Since this exogenous excess heat is high temperature, no new technology investments (for heat pumps or boilers)

Table 2

Natural gas, coal, and oil price assumptions for different scenarios based on IEA World Energy Outlook 2022 (Agency IE, 2022).

Fuel (€/GJ)	Net zero emissions by 2050				Stated policies			
	2025	2030	2040	2050	2025	2030	2040	2050
Natural gas	6.98	3.43	3.12	2.8	6.83	6.29	6.54	6.78
Coal	3.17	1.4	1.26	1.11	3.16	1.6	1.65	1.7
Oil	11.7	4.2	3.4	2.9	10.16	9.82	10.7	11.5

are considered for utilizing industrial excess heat in DH.

4.6. Policy scenarios

This section introduces the four policy scenarios considered in this study.

- **BH** - Benchmark scenario models the present policies of Denmark without any emission reduction targets. Similarly, no carbon tax is considered. As this paper study different decarbonization policies, this scenario represents the DH expansion, heat-saving investments, and fuel mix for the heating sector under no decarbonization policy. Thus, other scenarios with decarbonization policy can be compared with this one. This scenario uses natural gas, coal, and oil prices given in Table 2 under state policy column.
- **CP** - Climate policy scenario introduces carbon tax (appendix A4) and constraints on carbon emission, which correspond to targets set forth by the Danish government, leading to a reduction of 70% GHG emissions by 2030 (compared to 2005 level) and net-zero GHG emission in 2050. This scenario uses natural gas, coal, and oil prices given in Table 2 under net-zero emission column.
- **HS** - Heat-saving scenario exogenously imposed high levels of energy renovations resulting into 23.5 TWh reduction of heat demand in 2050 (or 75% heat demand reduction compared to 2020) on top of climate policy (CP) scenario. Such a high level of heat savings is motivated by the policy push for reducing energy demand by building renovation as proposed in fit-for-55 proposal (Piebalgs and Jones, 2021). For Denmark, the potential of heat savings achieved by implementing all the technical feasible energy renovation measures, irrespective of economic rationality, is about 23.5 TWh (Zvingilaite and Balyk, 2014). This scenario uses natural gas, coal, and oil prices given in Table 2 under net-zero emission column.
- **noNG** - No Gas scenario is built on top of the climate policy (CP) scenario and completely phase-out natural gas from the whole energy sector by 2030. This policy scenario is motivated by the Danish

government plan to phase-out natural gas entirely by 2030 at the onset of the 2022 war between Ukraine and Russia (Wienberg, 2022). This scenario uses natural gas, coal, and oil prices given in Table 2 under net-zero emission column.

The last three scenarios (CP, HS, & noNG) are collectively referred to as climate scenarios.

5. Results

5.1. Expansion of district heating (DH)

Fig. 4 shows the expansion of DH in 2050. In Denmark, the DH expansion is highest in the noNG scenario which represents that DH expansion can facilitate the earlier phase out of natural gas. After noNG, HS has the highest expansion this is due to substantial reduction in heat demand which result into very high share of cheap but exogenous industrial excess heat (discussed more in 5.3). A slightly higher DH expansion in BH scenario as compared to CP scenario is due to higher natural gas prices for individual heating in BH scenario which makes DH expansion competitive.

5.2. Heat-saving investments

Fig. 5 represents the resulting heat savings (or reduction in heat demand) achieved due to investments into heat-saving measures. Except for the policy driven aggressive renovations in HS scenario, no significant investment goes to heat savings in all the three scenarios. Among CP, noNG, and BH scenarios, BH scenario has the highest heat-saving investments due to high natural gas price assumption for BH which makes some investments into heat-saving measures optimal.

This represents heat saving renovations are a very expensive option than alternatives for an energy system with a high penetration of DH. However, it should be noted here that exogenous heat demand does

Fig. 5. Heat demand reduction achieved due to investment in heat saving measures (energy renovations) for HS scenario. The percentage represents the share of heat savings in each area compared to the total heat demand of each area.

consider some reduction in heat demand due investment into heat saving measures as already discussed (Fig. 3).

5.3. Development trends for fuel mix in DH sector

The fuel mix development trend for the DH sector for different scenarios is shown in Fig. 6.

A substantial difference in fuel mix exists between BH and climate scenarios. Within climate scenarios, the fuel mix of noNG is different

Fig. 4. Heat supplied by the District Heating under different scenarios in 2050. Blue colour represents heating demand covered by existing (non-expanded) DH network while red colour represents heat demand covered by expanded DH network. The absolute values of heat demand covered by expanded DH are shown. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. Fuel mix of annual energy production for different scenarios for District Heating sector. Wood pellets, straw, wood chip, & waste wood are grouped together in biomass. Similarly, raw biogas & upgraded biogas (or bio natural gas) is grouped into biogas.

from HS and CP. Substantial reduction in heat demand due to policy driven heat saving investments in HS scenario does not induce significant change in fuel mix as compared to CP scenarios.

In the BH scenario, share of natural gas increases towards 2050. In the absence of carbon tax, natural gas along with industrial waste heat, and municipal waste completely replace biofuels (biomass & biogas), oil, and coal.

In CP and HS scenario, natural gas is gradually phased out to meet emission targets while under noNG scenario, natural gas is phased out earlier. Under CP scenario, a considerable share of heat is produced from the natural gas due to very low prices under this scenario. However, the natural gas is ultimately phased-out. Relative to CP scenario, share of natural gas in heat production is lower in HS scenario due to low overall demand and sharp uptake of industrial excess heat.

Fuel mix comparison clearly highlight the significant role played by biogas, biomass, industrial excess heat, and electrification via heat pumps. In short to medium term, high consumption of biofuels and sharp uptake of industrial excess heat replaces coal, oil, and natural gas while in the long-term industrial excess heat and heat pumps captures the major share of DH. Most importantly, earlier phase-out of natural gas results into a very sharp uptake of heat pumps.

Due to exogenous industrial excess heat capacity and exogenous reduction in heat demand as result of heat-saving measures, HS scenario ends up with a very high share of excess heat, covering almost 50% of DH demand in 2050. Such a very high share of zero cost fuel makes DH very cheap and it's the primary reason behind a high expansion potential of DH as observed in Fig. 4. A reduction in exogenous excess heat capacity has most negative impact on DH expansion potential in HS scenario as compared to any other scenario (appendix D, also discussed later in this section).

In BH, the amount of municipal waste utilization mostly remains unchanged due to negative prices and fixed maximum potential. However, under climate scenarios municipal waste is not consumed a lot due to high emissions density. Some capacity of carbon capture and storage (CCS) towards the 2050 ensures negative emissions to achieve carbon emission target. Solar thermal doesn't play a significant role due to low solar resource in Denmark and due to the fact that DH is suitable in urban centres which lack the space for solar fields. The coal and light oil

are entirely removed from the system due to Danish government regulation to completely phase out these fuels out by 2030. The build-up of thermal storage capacity represents more investments into long-term inter-seasonal storage (see Appendix C2). The climate scenarios have an earlier uptake of thermal storage as compared to BH scenario. Further supplementary results are represented in appendix C including generation technology mix for the DH and fuel mix of the power sector in Denmark.

5.4. Development trends of fuel mix for individual heating sector

A quick overview of fuel mix for individual heating sector is depicted in Fig. 7. The fuel mix doesn't differ considerable among the climate scenarios. For the individual heating sector, decarbonization is achieved by massive uptake of power-to-heat via individual heat pumps and upgraded biogas – also referred to as bio natural gas. The upgraded biogas readily replaces natural gas without any investment into new technology. Due to very low natural gas prices in climate scenarios, exogenous biogas is replaced by the natural gas for short-term. However, to ultimately meet the carbon targets, natural gas is completely phased-out by the electrification and biogas uptake.

5.5. Essential role played by biofuels

Biofuels play an important in decarbonizing the Danish energy sector. The yearly consumption of some of the biofuels, namely, straw, wood chips, and biogas is restricted based on the locally available potential to ensure sustainable consumption(as mentioned in Table 1). Fig. 8 depicts the total utilization of such biofuels under different policy scenarios.

BH scenario has the lowest overall utilization of biofuels. CP and HS have higher utilization of biofuels as compared to BH while there is small difference between CP and HS. The noNG scenario has the highest utilization of biofuels. The consumption of biofuels is especially very high during short and medium term. Among the various biofuels, biogas has the highest consumption due to its ability to replace natural gas and negative emissions attributed to it. Such a high utilization of biofuels can substantially strain the supply chain rendering them unsustainable.

Fig. 7. Fuel mix of annual energy produced for individual heating sector.

Fuel	Scenario	2020	2025	2030	2040	2050
Biogas	BH	13%	1%	1%	0%	
	CP	12%	100%	100%	86%	92%
	HS	13%	100%	100%	72%	58%
	noNG	12%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Straw	BH	94%	100%	32%		
	CP	84%	100%	100%	38%	63%
	HS	100%	100%	100%	36%	61%
	noNG	84%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Woodchips	BH	85%	28%	8%		
	CP	99%	100%	18%	10%	38%
	HS	85%	100%	17%	12%	71%
	noNG	99%	100%	100%	44%	58%

Fig. 8. Percentage utilization of biofuels out of the total available potential. Biogas includes raw biogas and upgraded biogas (biomethane).

5.6. Total system cost

From the total system cost perspective (Fig. 9), HS scenario is the most expensive one due to forced investments in expensive energy renovations, which contributes to the strong decline in demand but also substantially to the overall system cost. As expected, BH scenarios is the cheapest one, mainly due to no costs assigned to emissions. A small difference of about 0.07% in the total system cost between noNG & CP scenario represents the long-term feasibility of earlier natural gas phase out.

5.7. Sensitivity analysis

As noted from Fig. 6, exogenous industrial excess heat (EH) occupies a major share of DH sector. While the utilization of industrial excess heat in DH is both technical and economically possible. However, such arrangement often requires inclusion of a very diverse players into DH network which is often complicated. Therefore, a sensitivity analysis is conducted by reducing this exogenous capacity by 50%. The results are depicted in Fig. 10.

The results show an uptake of natural gas combined with CCS for CP

and HS scenarios which is due to very low prices for natural gas and target to achieve emission reduction. The uptake of more heat pumps is also observed. For the noNG scenario, reduction in industrial excess heat leads to further uptake of heat pumps. In addition to heat pumps uptake of municipal waste combined with CCS is also observed for all the climate scenarios.

Similarly, as biomass plays an important role in decarbonization, its uptake is facilitated by the lack of any fuel tax. Therefore, another sensitivity analysis is conducted by introducing fuel tax of 7.37 €/GJ on biomass, which is calculated equivalent to electricity tax by normalizing for energy content (OECD., 2018). The results are shown in Fig. 11.

A fuel tax on biomass leads to decrease in its consumption in all the climate scenarios. Here again the uptake of natural gas combined with CCS is observed for CP and HS scenarios. The uptake of heat pumps is slightly decreased. For noNG scenario, however, heat pumps uptake replaces the natural gas uptake observed in CP and HS scenarios. An important trend can be observed in all the three scenarios where a fuel tax on biomass reduces its raw use while at the same time promote biomass consumption in combination with CCS. Thus, a fuel tax on biomass promotes its sustainable use.

Further sensitivity analyses have found that investment into heat

Fig. 9. Total system cost (a)represents total system cost for all the scenarios, (b) represents system cost difference from the BH scenario.

Fig. 10. Fuel mix change compared to base scenario with 50% reduction in exogenous Excess Heat capacity.

savings measures (energy renovations) are sensitive to cost of heat savings. A 50% reduction in cost of energy saving renovations results into about 2.5 TWh of heat demand reduction (about 9%) in CP, and noNG scenarios. Such heat demand reduction is still very small compared to what is assumed in HS scenario (i.e. 23.5 TWh). Thus, it can be concluded that investment into heat savings doesn't play a major role. Investments into heat-saving measures are also found to be sensitive to the fuel tax on biomass and increase in DH expansion cost. Both of these sensitivity analyses show an increased investment into heat-saving measures. Expansion of district heating network is sensitive to cost of expansion where a 50% reduction in expansion cost results into 49%–112% increase in DH network expansion. A tax on biomass also leads to more expansion of the DH network. A detailed list and outcome of sensitivity analysis is represented in appendix D.

6. Discussion

The implication of the results obtained in the previous section is

discussed from policy and private business perspectives in the following.

6.1. Policy & regulatory perspective

District heating plays an important role in the decarbonization of the Danish energy system. DH, which is already mature, sees its share increase in all the scenarios. Although in terms of numbers, the expansion of DH in different scenarios is between 4 and 6% which doesn't look significant. However, as DH is already mature in Denmark, an expansion of 4–6% can be regarded as significant. Another study also found similar expansion potential for conventional DH in Denmark (Nielsen and Grundahl, 2018). However, this study only considers conventional DH networks, the low temperature or 4th generation DH is not considered.

Due to the current policy push (Piebalgs and Jones, 2021), a major share of buildings will undergo energy renovations. Such renovations should be planned carefully as our sensitivity analysis shows about 9% potential for heat savings when heat saving renovations cost is reduced. While investments into energy savings are not an efficient pathway to

Fig. 11. Fuel mix change compared to base scenario with introduction of biomass tax.

achieve decarbonization from an energy system cost perspective, policy-driven energy saving investments may encompass some other goals like self-sufficiency or reduced reliance on energy imports. These goals are very valid, but out of the scope of this study.

As the natural gas is ultimately phased-out in all the climate scenarios, its earlier phase-out by 2030 can be made possible at a very little addition cost by promoting alternatives, especially biofuels and power-to-heat. The European Commission's RePowerEU plan (Commission E, 2022), put out in response to 2022 Ukraine-Russia war, aim to mobilize biomethane (upgraded biogas) to reduce the reliance on imported natural gas. However, such a fast uptake of biofuels can strain their supply chain.

In all the climate scenarios decarbonization is achieved with industrial excess heat and biofuels (biomass & biogas), and electrification via heat pumps. High use of biomass is cautioned as biomass is renewable only in limited qualities (Harjanne and Korhonen, 2019) and in the future, it faces more competition from other sectors like aviation, the marine shipping industry, and land transport for decarbonization (Østergaard et al., 2019). Therefore, a future high competition for biomass may lead to increase in prices. This situation is somewhat similar to the sensitivity analysis conducted in this study with a fuel tax on biomass. A fuel tax on biomass reduces high reliance on biomass. The fuel tax also promotes sustainable consumption of biomass (with CCS) while reducing its raw use (without CCS).

All the climate scenarios have a very high electrification via heat pumps. Earlier natural gas phase out even promotes more uptake of heat pumps. In the individual heating sector, the decarbonization is also achieved by a high share of electrification via heat pumps. Therefore, uptake of large-scale heat pumps in DH networks requires strong carbon emission reduction policies. While a number of studies have found a limited profitability of central heat pumps in the existing district heating systems (Bach et al., 2016) (Østergaard et al., 2019) (Lygnerud et al., 2021), other studies have found that the electrification of DH via heat pumps can be promoted by changing tariff designs (Østergaard and Andersen, 2021; Songa et al., 2016; Lyden and Tuohy, 2022), (Bergantze and Gunkel, 2022; Volkova et al., 2022) and a reduction in DH supply temperature (Averfalk and Werner, 2020). Furthermore, an uptake of heat pumps requires better understanding of operating heat pumps in different electricity markets as the uptake of heat pumps exposes the DH sector to the uncertainty of the power market prices. Also, a large uptake of heat pumps can have an impact on electricity distribution network. Since energy system model used for this study doesn't model the distribution network, studying impact of heat pumps on power sector merits further investigation.

A DH network is typically comprised of dedicated heat producers and

heat users. Utilization of excess heat (EH) therefore requires opening of closed DH network to new players. That will require a comprehensive regulatory framework encompassing standardized contracts along with third-party access. EU recently passed a law on third-party access; however, it falls short to tick all the boxes (Holzleitner et al., 2020). Most of the regulations on renewable energy and energy efficiency doesn't recognize excess heat as renewable rather, it is often attributed as an undesirable product that needs to be eliminated (Lygnerud et al., 2019). Denmark recently reduces the tax on selling excess heat, an apparent positive signal to recognize its potential towards future decarbonized energy systems (Nielsen, 2021). Furthermore, a switch to low supply temperature also enhance the potential of excess heat utilization as most of locally available excess heat is of low temperature (Persson and Münster, 2016).

6.2. District heating companies' perspective

Conventional business models of district heating revolve around production and supply of heat, and the district heating business is often regarded as a natural monopoly. DH is often subjected to price controls as, for example, in the Netherlands (Liu et al., 2019) and in Denmark (Danish Energy Agency et al., 2012). Sweden is the only exception that has undergone a change from price control to liberalized pricing of DH (Egüez, 2021). Such monopolistic character of DH limits the prospect of the business model innovation for district heating companies as opposed to any other private company or firm. Lygnerud K (Lygnerud, 2019) identified the business model logic of DH companies relates to centralized production and economy of scale. Similarly, Sandoff A et al. (Sandoff and Williamsson, 2015) further add a dimension of long-term contracts with suppliers and consumers due to large sunk investment into the DH network.

As depicted in the results, presently DH in Denmark also relies quite significantly on large CHP based capacity, where DH companies shift most of the operating cost of CHP to DH consumers and earn their profit on electricity market (Danish Energy Agency, 2016). However, as shown in the results, future decarbonization reduce the share of CHP based capacity which threatens the present business model. Further, DH in Denmark is already mature with a high share of market penetration. A low potential expansion in the future ultimately signals the saturation of the heating market. Under the above mentioned challenges, DH companies can adapt their business models offering more energy services and actively engaging with customers and stakeholders, as suggested in (Sandoff and Williamsson, 2015) (Ahvenniemi and Klobut, 2014) (Lygnerud, 2018).

The DH companies which are facing a saturated market could offer a

magnitude of energy services that could vary from conducting initial feasibility studies to managing and operating energy assets. This could also enable DH companies to provide services and solutions to consumers outside of the DH network by offering services like, planning, installing, monitoring, and operating individual heat pumps (Åberg et al., 2020; Ahvenniemi and Klobut, 2014) (Lygnerud et al., 2021). However, it should be noted here that to offer the above-mentioned energy services, DH companies need to adapt to digitization and dynamic/hourly pricing as they are enablers for such services (Østergaard and Andersen, 2021; Songa et al., 2016).

The heat pumps facilitate the integration of renewable energy, but they also expose district heating to the uncertainty of electricity market prices due to the increased share of renewable energy in the future. This merits further investigation on how that would impact the revenues. Utilization of excess heat brings in new players with diverging view on value of excess heat, which makes the negotiations process more complicated while at the consumption side, the green value of excess heat is not widely recognized, making it difficult to capitalize on it (Lygnerud et al., 2019).

7. Conclusion & policy implications

Understanding the future development of DH sector is essential for an affordable energy transition. In addition to decarbonization goals, DH sector faces challenges from an unreliable natural gas supply, which currently forms a major share of the current DH generation. Similarly, the profitability of DH depends on high heat demand density. However, massive policy-driven investments into heat-saving renovations reduce this heat demand density which can reduce the profitability of DH. Therefore, in this article, we analyse the future development of DH from an energy system perspective under different decarbonization policy scenarios. Our findings highlight important implications for the different stakeholders.

Decarbonization of DH is achieved by a mix of fuels and technologies, including Biofuels (biomass & biogas), industrial excess heat, and electrification via heat pumps. Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) is an enabler for biomass and municipal waste to achieve net negative emissions for the energy sector. The different scenarios studied in this article offer following interesting policy implications:

Biofuels are especially important for decarbonization under all the policy scenarios related to net-zero emissions by 2050. An earlier natural gas phase-out further increases biofuels' consumption, especially for the short to medium term, leading to the utilization of almost all the available potential. Such a high utilization of biofuels put a strain on their supply chain. Our analysis shows that a biomass fuel tax promotes sustainable use of biomass (combined with CCS) while reducing its raw use (without CCS).

Our analysis shows that a policy scenario with an earlier phase-out of natural gas is quite possible from the system cost perspective, as it only inflicts 0.07% additional cost as compared to a policy scenario with only carbon neutral target by 2050. The earlier phase-out of natural gas is made possible by a) higher consumption of biofuels, b) faster and more electrification of the heating sector, and c) expansion of DH network.

Electrification of the heating sector via heat pumps plays an important role in decarbonising the energy system which faces challenges of uncertain natural gas supply and very high reliance on biofuels. Our analysis has shown that a lack of any carbon policy (carbon tax or

emissions limits or both) leads to almost no uptake of heat pumps at DH and individual heating sector. Thus, carbon policies promote electrification of heating sector vis heat pumps.

The share of DH is expected to increase by 4–6% under different policy scenarios even in the presence of an already mature market share in Denmark. The future expansion potential of DH is found to depend on the following important factors: a) earlier natural gas phase-out led to the highest expansion of DH. Thus, DH facilitates earlier phase-out of natural gas due to fuel diversification. b) our analysis shows that the expansion of DH is very sensitive to the cost of expansion. Therefore, DH expansion and development should be promoted along with other infrastructural development projects (i.e. road constructions) as they bring down the cost of DH expansion.

The policy for massive investment into energy-saving measures or energy renovations to reduce heat demand is not optimal from an overall energy system cost perspective. However, our analysis doesn't consider other policy objectives like self-sufficiency. The reduction in heat-saving measures cost can lead up to 2.5 TWh (9% of total heat demand) of heat savings potential in 2050 to be optimal without any heat-saving enforcement. But such energy savings are far less ambitious than the targets outlined in the recent fit-for-55 proposal and RePowerEU plan.

The DH sector at present has a high share of CHP-based capacity, which enable DH companies to earn profit from the power market as DH operations are non-profit in Denmark. Our results show that this CHP-based capacity will reduce in the future. The implication of such development on the business model of conventional DH companies merits further investigation.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Muhammad Bilal Siddique: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Per Sieverts Nielsen:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Mathias Berg Rosendal:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization. **Ida Græsted Jensen:** Data curation, Methodology. **Dogan Keles:** Conceptualization, Validation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix

Appendix A. Assumptions

A1. District Heating (DH) expansion potential and cost

The expansion cost is based on heat demand density and distance from the existing district heating network. Only the expansion of the existing DH grid to nearby buildings and buildings located within the DH grid is considered. For the former, the cost of distribution grid expansion along with connection cost is included towards the final expansion cost, while for the latter only connection cost is considered.

Table A1
District Heating (DH) expansion potential and cost.

DH areas	Individual heat areas	Expansion	Potential [MWh]	Cost [EUR/MWh]
DK1_Large	DK1_NoDH_ind	Inside DH	24061.5	10.8957
DK1_Large	DK1_NoDH_ind	Near DH	88370.4	26.7767
DK1_Large	DK1_NoDH_apart	Inside DH	19486.2	5.63829
DK1_Large	DK1_NoDH_apart	Near DH	5552.29	27.0269
DK1_Rural	DK1_NoDH_ind	Inside DH	349616	10.8859
DK1_Rural	DK1_NoDH_ind	Near DH	686601	53.8847
DK1_Rural	DK1_NoDH_apart	Inside DH	73338.7	10.1208
DK1_Rural	DK1_NoDH_apart	Near DH	61429.9	45.3
DK1_Medium	DK1_NoDH_ind	Inside DH	148940	10.5248
DK1_Medium	DK1_NoDH_ind	Near DH	154314	81.6286
DK1_Medium	DK1_NoDH_apart	Inside DH	55119.5	7.5686
DK1_Medium	DK1_NoDH_apart	Near DH	17845.1	59.3228
DK2_Large	DK2_NoDH_ind	Inside DH	157105	10.9462
DK2_Large	DK2_NoDH_ind	Near DH	78729.2	27.3874
DK2_Large	DK2_NoDH_apart	Inside DH	379582	2.67121
DK2_Large	DK2_NoDH_apart	Near DH	55742.2	42.0754
DK2_Rural	DK2_NoDH_ind	Inside DH	181877	10.9237
DK2_Rural	DK2_NoDH_ind	Near DH	1.45E+06	18.3975
DK2_Rural	DK2_NoDH_apart	Inside DH	71975.6	7.77373
DK2_Rural	DK2_NoDH_apart	Near DH	449193	15.5516
DK2_Medium	DK2_NoDH_ind	Inside DH	123952	10.4242
DK2_Medium	DK2_NoDH_ind	Near DH	253622	23.2728
DK2_Medium	DK2_NoDH_apart	Inside DH	94068.5	5.99125
DK2_Medium	DK2_NoDH_apart	Near DH	57439.7	27.8952
DK2_MedSmall	DK2_NoDH_ind	Inside DH	70604.4	10.9043
DK2_MedSmall	DK2_NoDH_ind	Near DH	194406	31.7922
DK2_MedSmall	DK2_NoDH_apart	Inside DH	41048.5	7.91984
DK2_MedSmall	DK2_NoDH_apart	Near DH	76564.6	20.7907
DK1_Small	DK1_NoDH_ind	Inside DH	107138	10.8087
DK1_Small	DK1_NoDH_ind	Near DH	92047.5	127.285
DK1_Small	DK1_NoDH_apart	Inside DH	20557.6	11.4084
DK1_Small	DK1_NoDH_apart	Near DH	6935.14	100.265
DK1_MedSmall	DK1_NoDH_ind	Inside DH	41208.5	10.6239
DK1_MedSmall	DK1_NoDH_ind	Near DH	97285.7	74.7178
DK1_MedSmall	DK1_NoDH_apart	Inside DH	22489.7	4.92516
DK1_MedSmall	DK1_NoDH_apart	Near DH	30249.3	33.8603
DK2_Small	DK2_NoDH_ind	Inside DH	14637.2	10.7735
DK2_Small	DK2_NoDH_ind	Near DH	248919	18.3191
DK2_Small	DK2_NoDH_apart	Inside DH	5961.49	14.6849
DK2_Small	DK2_NoDH_apart	Near DH	32945.1	19.2619

ind = houses; apart = Apartments.

A2: Cost curves for investment into heat savings measures (energy renovations)

Fig. A2. Cost curves for investment into heat savings measures (energy renovations) for different heating areas.

A3: Fuel price assumptions

List of all the fuels modelled and corresponding fuel prices.

Fuel	Price assumption (€/GJ)				Maximum Potential (Pj/year)	Source of Fuel price assumption
	2020	2030	2040	2050		
Municipal waste	-3.295	-3.295	-3.295	-3.295	40.7	Münster and Meibom (2011)
Straw	5.66	5.95	6	6.14	20	Danish Energy Agency (2021)
Wood chips	6.56	6.96	7.28	7.28	40	Danish Energy Agency (2021)
Wood pellets	8.57	9.15	9.25	9.35	-	Danish Energy Agency (2021)
Biogas	9.997	9.997	9.997	9.997	16.8	Jensen et al. (2017)
Nuclear	0.4606	0.4606	0.4606	0.4606	-	ENTSO-E. (2018)
Shale	2.254	2.254	2.254	2.254	-	ENTSO-E. (2018)
Peat	1.38	1.86	1.81	1.77	-	ENTSO-E. (2018)
Biomethane	18	18	18	18	-	Scarlat et al. (2018)

A4: Carbon price projections

Table A4

Carbon price projection based on IEA World Energy Outlook 2022 - Net zero emission scenario (Agency IE, 2022).

Year	Carbon price (€/tonne)
2020	40
2025	100

(continued on next page)

Table A4 (continued)

Year	Carbon price (£/tonne)
2030	140
2040	205
2050	250

Appendix C. Supplementary Results

C1: GHG emissions

Fig. C1. GHG emissions based on type of emissions - CH4 & CO2.

C2: Storage capacity

Fig. C2. Yearly thermal storage capacity change (commissioning and decommissioning) for District heating.

C3: Technology generation mix – District heating

Fig. C3. Net yearly capacity addition for District Heating.

C4: Power sector fuel mix

Fig. C4. Annual energy produced by the power sector.

C5: Fuel mix for industry sector

Fig. C5. Annual energy produced by the process industry sector.

C6: Generation technology mix based on fuel – District heating

Fig. C6. Generation technology mix based on fuel – District heating.

Appendix D. Sensitivity analysis

Table D

List of all sensitivity analyses and their outcomes. Change % presents percentage change from the base scenarios.

Sensitivity Analysis	Heat Savings % change to base scenario			DH expansion % change to base scenario		
	CP	HS	noNG	CP	HS	noNG
Tax on Biomass	112	0	99	34	34	23
DH expansion cost decrease by 50%	-3	0	-2	122	72	49
DH expansion cost increase by 50%	93	0	73	-23	-34	-43
Heat saving cost decrease by 50%	2112*	0	1656**	17	4	1
Heat saving cost increase by 50%	-11	0	-10	1	0	1
Reduced Excess Heat capacity by 50%	70	0	58	-1	-6	-1

* 2.5 TWh of additional heat savings.

** 2.4 TWh of additional heat savings.

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